

A PROJECT REPORT

ON

**DETERMINATION OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTION OF SOILS
AROUND DUMPSITES IN NEKEDE.**

BY

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SUBMITTED TO

**DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY
SCHOOL OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES**

**FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
OWERRI (FUTO).**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF BACHELOR OF TECHNOLOGY (B.TECH). DEGREE IN
INDUSTRIAL CHEMISTRY.**

AUGUST, 2023.

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project work on " A Determination Of Heavy Metal Pollution Of
Soils Around Dumpsites" was done by Oguike Kaosisochukwu Allwell (Reg No.

20171044485) in partial fulfillment of the award of a Bachelor's degree (B.Tech.) in chemistry from the Federal University of Technology, Owerri.

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SOILS AROUND DUMPSITES IN NEKEDE was prepared by **OGUIKE
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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to God Almighty for his loving kindness, support, grace and faithfulness throughout the course of this research work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I remain grateful to Almighty God for his Mercies thus far in this journey. My profound gratitude goes to my supervisor Dr. Ali Bilar, who has been a guide since the commencement of this work. His understanding and better insight towards my project work, is greatly admired.

Also worthy, is my Head of department, Prof. C.K.ENENEBEAKU, my course Adviser Dr. R. C. ANOZIE, will be greatly remembered for their fatherly roles . I am greatly indebted to the great staff of Chemistry department for all the knowledge acquired.

Also, my parents Mr. & Mrs. MICHAEL OGUIKE, my Uncle Mr. KINGSLEY OGUIKE my Aunty, Mrs. AMAKA NNODI , Mrs. FLORENCE IWU, Sir GEORGE BESTMAN AKALUKA, Mrs. ETHEL ABALEKE for their financial support and advise towards my academic pursuit. I am forever grateful.

ABSTRACT

The Analysis of Heavy metals from the dumpsite soil was carried out using AAS – model (Atomic Absorption spectroscopy) model. The result statement shows that, cadmium (Cd), Mercury (Hg) and lead (Pb), chromium (Cr) and iron (Fe) are present in a higher concentration. Soil sampling & Analysis, identifies the need for an improved waste management in order to safeguard soil quality and the environment (Nekede).

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Heavy metal Pollution around dumpsites is a significant environmental concern due to its potential health hazards and impacts on plants and animal life [1]. A comparative determination of heavy metal pollution, involves evaluating the concentrations of heavy metals in soils around different dumpsites [2]. and comparing these levels to regulatory guidelines/limits that is suitable.

The Process of determining heavy metal pollution begins with the sampling of soils from various locations. The samples are then prepared for analysis, using various techniques, including digestion and acid extraction [3].

The heavy metals concentrations are then determined using analytical techniques, such as Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy or inductively coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry. The results obtained from the analysis are compared with regulatory guidelines for heavy metals in soils. In Nigeria, The National Environmental Standards and Regulation

Enforcement Agency(NESREA), a parastatal under the Federal Ministry of Environment, provides regulatory guidelines for heavy metal concentration in soils. The acceptable limits for heavy metals vary on the type of metal and its intended use.

Overall, a comparative determination of heavy metal pollution is a critical step in assessing the environmental health impact of dumpsites [4]. It also help to identify various sites that require immediate action, to stop pollution, protect human lives and environmental health generally.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The urbanization and industrial growth have given rise to an alarming surge in waste generation, leading to the establishment of dumpsites as a solution for waste disposal. However, these dumpsites have the potential to become sources of heavy metal pollution, endangering both the environment and human health [5]. This study seeks to bridge this gap by systematically evaluating and comparing the concentrations of key heavy metals in dumpsite soils, shedding light on the potential risks posed and the toxic effect that limit waste management [6].

1.3 Objectives

The main objective of this work is to identify the various levels of heavy metals present in soil samples, collected from the three(3) dumpsites.

Furthermore, the research would also aim at the following:

- i. Identification of heavy metal pollution in the various soil samples.
- ii. Compare the various heavy metals pollution levels of the dumpsites.
- iii. Provide a comprehensive summary of our findings and its implication for future

research

iv. Provide guidance on effective measures, in order to control the adverse effects of heavy metal pollution.

v. Contribute to a vast knowledge of heavy metal pollution in the affected areas(dumpsites)

1.4 Scope of Study

The scope of study of the determination of heavy metal pollution of soils in dumpsites involves analyzing the presence and levels of various heavy metals, such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and other waste materials found in these sites. This study typically encompasses sampling methods, laboratory analysis techniques, risk assessment, environmental impact evaluation, and potential health implications for both ecosystems and human populations that are exposed to these metals.

1.5 Aim

The primary aim of this project is to assess the levels of heavy metal pollution across different dumpsites within Nekede, with the specific objective of understanding the extent and variability of heavy metal contamination in these dumpsites and also enhance the understanding of heavy metal pollution originating from dumpsites, thereby informing policy decisions, waste management practices, and environmental protection efforts.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Historical review of heavy metals present in dumpsites

Heavy metal pollution of soils around dumpsites is a major environmental and public health concern globally. Heavy metals are non-biodegradable, and toxic to the environment. They can also accumulate in soil and plants, posing a great risk [7]. In this study, we aim to evaluate different research that has been conducted to determine the

extent of heavy metal pollution in soils around dumpsites.

Heavy metals e.g Iron and Nickel, are very essential for the survival of life in low concentrations. Also, Anthropogenic activities introduced recently to the eco-system, has caused great human exposure to heavy metals and the contamination of soils around the dumpsites.

A proper waste disposal has become a serious problem in the Nekede Axis, which has greatly shown, the adverse effects it has caused to humans and the environment [8].

2.2 Origin and distribution

Waste is dumped recklessly with no regard to environmental implications, while some are burnt in the open and ashes abandoned at the sites. The burning of wastes, gets rid of all combustible materials and oxidize the metals, leaving the leftover ash very rich in heavy metals. After the oxidation and corrosion process, the metals dissolve in rain water and leach(infiltrate) into the soil, which is being picked up by growing plants entering the food chain [9].

Improper waste management, results in the contamination of the environment.

Dumpsites emit odours that cause illness to people. The various health issues, ranges from respiratory problems, skin irritation, Nose and Eyes irritation, psychological disorders, gastrointestinal problems and allergies [10]. Unconsolidated solid wastes also obstruct good stream flow, resulting to the formation of water bodies, that become breeding grounds for disease causing organisms e.g mosquitoes.

The abandoned sites can be turned for various useful purposes, such as crop cultivation, human residences, recreational centers etc. The soil present in these dumpsites is evacuated for amendments because of its rich mineral and organic

content which is of great benefit to man.

2.3 Behavior of inorganic (heavy metals) contamination in soils

The most common group of elements which are present in the soil, are mainly the transition metals also known as heavy metals e.g Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Zinc (Zn), Mercury (Ag), Arsenic (As), Chromium (Cr), Cadmium (Cd), Aluminium (Al), Nickel (Ni) etc. These metals occur greatly in the soil due to the excessive waste materials present in the dumpsites.

2.4 Copper

Copper is a widely naturally occurring element used in the society. It could be an inorganic metal in industrial and agricultural applications. It is an essential nutrient for both plants and animals, excessive amounts of copper can contaminate the soil and have adverse effects on soil ecosystems and human health [11].

The primary source of copper contamination in soils is through mining, smelting, the use of copper based fungicides and pesticides in agriculture. It also leaches from copper plumbing, industrial wastes, leading to a large contamination of the soil.

Once copper gets into the soil, it can bind to the soil particles or organic matter and undergo various transformations (Oxidation and Reduction) which affects its mobility, bioavailability and toxicity to soil organisms and plants. Copper contamination also leads to reduces soil fertility, altered microbial activity, and impaired plant growth and development [12].

To mitigate copper contamination in soils, proper measures are taken, such as, waste management, the use of copper alternatives in agriculture and the adoption of

sustainable soil management practices are necessary. Furthermore, the implementation of environmental regulations and monitoring programs can help to limit the exposure of soils and humans to excessive levels of copper.

The various reactions that occur with copper in dumpsites are given as follows:

i. Reaction with Sulfur Compounds

Copper can react with sulphur compounds present in the environment to form copper sulphide compounds:

ii. Reaction with Water and Carbon Dioxide

Copper can react with water and carbon dioxide from the air to form copper carbonate, a greenish particle often seen on aged copper surfaces.

iii. Reaction with Alkaline Substances

Copper can react with alkaline substances like ammonia in order to form copper amine complexes.

iv. Electrochemical Reactions

In dumpsites with varying metal compositions, electrochemical reactions can occur, leading to galvanic corrosion. This involves the transfer of electrons between different metals and copper, accelerating the degradation process.

These reactions can lead to the formation of various compounds and contribute to the overall deterioration of copper objects in dumpsites.

Fig. 2.1.

[13]. Characterization of heavy metal pollution in Anthropogenic and geologically influenced semi arid regions.

2.5 Iron

Iron is an essential micronutrient for plants and soils, that naturally exists in the soil [14]. However, the excessive concentrations of iron, have huge detrimental effects on soils. The behaviour iron exhibits, is influenced by various factors namely: Soil pH, Organic matter content, redox potential and the presence of other mineral constituents [15].

In terms of heavy metals concentration, iron itself is not considered as a toxic metal [16]. However, high levels of iron concentration in the soil can affect the availability and the presence of essential nutrients such as zinc, manganese and copper, which can lead to nutrient imbalance in plants. The toxic nature of iron can also occur in soils with a higher level of sensitivity to iron content [17].

They can be ascertained via the following ways:

i. Soil pH - The availability of iron in soil is strongly influenced by pH. In acidic

soils(with a pH level below 6) iron is more soluble and readily available, while in alkaline soils(pH levels above 7) iron tends to form an insoluble compound making it less available for plant life and can lead to a deficiency of plants growing around alkaline soils.

ii. Redox potential - The redox potential of soil, indicates the availability of oxygen (behaviour of iron under aerobic and anaerobic conditions, oxygen rich and deficient conditions). It can promote the conversion of iron from a reduced state (ferrous) to an oxidized state (ferric) which leads to an increased presence of heavy metals like iron. This also limits their bioavailability and mobility.

However, under anaerobic conditions, iron can be reduced to its soluble form (Fe^{2+}), which is more available. Excessive water logging, poor drainage systems can also lead anaerobic conditions and increases iron availability. It can be illustrated via the following:

- i. Reduction of iron (III) oxide (Fe_2O_3) to Iron (II) oxide (FeO)
- ii. Oxidation of Iron (II) oxide (FeO) to Iron (III) oxide (Fe_2O_3)
- iii. Oxidation of Ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) to Ferric iron (Fe^{3+})
- iv. Reduction of Ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) to Ferrous iron (Fe^{2+})

The balance between oxidation and reduction, is greatly influenced by redox potential.

Other Factors May Include:

i. Organic matter content - This plays an important role in iron behavior in soil. It can form various complexes that can enhance iron availability to plants [18]. Organic matter can influence soil pH and redox potential indirectly affecting iron availability, various

soils with a low organic content, can also have lower iron availability.

A good understanding of the behavior of iron in soils is of great importance [19]. For effective management of soil fertility, optimal plant growth, regular soil testing/ amendments which can help to maintain a defined balanced iron level, and prevent further nutrient imbalance in agriculture.

2.6 Chromium

Chromium is greatly influenced by various factors namely: ecological, anthropogenic, geological and the environment.

They also pose a great challenge to human health and safety [20].

Chromium mostly exists in trivalent Cr (III) or hexavalent Cr (VI) oxidation states, which greatly impacts soil behaviour. Cr (III) is less mobile and also less toxic to Cr (VI), which is soluble and can also leach into the soil as a groundwater. It also absorbs soil particles in larger quantity, thereby increasing the pH level of the soil which is more favourable to the trivalent chromium absorption rate and a lesser pH level makes the hexavalent chromium to a less mobile state. Although Cr(VI) which is more soluble, can leach deeply into the soil and contaminate the groundwater [21].

The mobility (movement) is much affected by pH and redox condition/levels. Also, Cr (VI) around acidic soils, can help enhance its mobility and reduce its solubility drastically. Other processes such as mining, waste disposal can significantly increase the level of chromium in the soil.

A proper monitoring/good management of metal concentrations in chromium requires a very knowledgeable understanding of complex interaction between soil properties, environmental conditions & human/industrial activities.

2.7 Cadmium

Cadmium mostly accumulates in the soil, largely due to mainly industrial, mining and agricultural practices, enhances a large deposit to the soil.

It does not naturally occur in the soil as a free metal. It is also not essential for plant growth, and excess of it is toxic to plant and human life.

In aqueous solutions, cadmium occurs as a divalent cation Cd^{2+} , pH levels also influence greatly the mobility of cadmium due to metal hydrolysis, ion pair formation, organic matter solubility, oxy-hydroxides surface charges, and edges of clay. When the pH level increases, various metal retention to mineral surface increases, through precipitation and adsorption [22].

Due to its specific hydrochemical characteristics, it has the potential to ensure the mobility of groundwater in the soil. Stable dissolved complexes are also formed, with both organic and inorganic ligands which inhibits absorption and precipitation (other cations such as calcium, iron and manganese can compete with cadmium for adsorption sites on soil particles) [23].

A good understanding of the absorption and precipitation process of cadmium behavior in soils, is very important for managing cadmium contamination in soils. Techniques that can be used to obtain a solution to solve the problem (contamination) are namely: adjusting pH levels, addition of amendments to facilitate adsorption and redox condition management.

Fig. 2.2

[24]. A cadmium contaminated soil.

2.8 Arsenic

Arsenic mainly exists as a naturally occurring metal(arsenite As(III) and arsenate ions As(v), it is an essential metal that is toxic after being ingested into the soil at higher levels, in combination with oxygen, chlorine, and sulphur in order to form inorganic arsenic compounds. Various factors such as human activities and environmental conditions (soil contamination) [25].

It also plays a role in the presence of arsenic in the soil. Its characterization(behaviour) largely depends on its chemical form, solubility, soil interaction with particles and environmental factors. Leaching into the soil groundwater can take place, after particles have adhered to each other. Various reactions can be used to illustrate the presence of arsenic in soils

i. Adsorption - This involves the replacement of hydroxide ions (OH⁻) on the mineral surface, thereby forming an inner sphere complex

ii. Reduction - it also undergoes an oxidation- reduction reaction, when arsenic leaches on to soil minerals, but rather it is very mobile due to the lower charge it possesses.

iii. Plant uptake - This mainly involves taking up arsenic from the root of plants, primarily in the form of an arsenate, mostly phosphates. The phosphates can also be replaced by the arsenates, when a metabolic process takes place in the plants roots.

Overall, an exposure to arsenic at longer periods of time, can cause skin disorder/ irritation to humans after being ingested at various levels, loss of soil fertility which affects agricultural productivity and toxic waste effluents from dumpsites.

2.9 Aluminium

The behaviour of aluminum is greatly influenced majorly by its chemical form and its interaction with the soil components. The existence of aluminum in various forms, depend mostly on its solubility and soil pH level. Al^{3+} is mostly released into various soil solutions, as a result of mineral weathering. (A huge breakdown of the soil into physical and chemical components). aluminum can also be transported through soil layers and leach into the soil as a groundwater [26]. The transport medium may depend on factors like soil texture, drainage, and organic matter content.

aluminum can also bind with phosphates ions, in order to form insoluble compounds that limit its availability (Availability of phosphorus) to plants. This process affects both nutrient uptake and plant growth.

Acidic soils also act in this kind of way also, they tend to raise the pH and decrease the solubility of aluminum after lime has been added, it rather helps limit aluminum toxicity and improve soil fertility.

In a nutshell, aluminum behavior to the soil is mainly related to its chemical forms, its various interactions with soil soil components, environmental conditions such as soil pH level etc. a good understanding of these interaction mechanisms ,is essential for managing soil health and optimizing plant growth in an agricultural setting.

2.10 Exposure of humans to heavy metals

Exposure to heavy metals, such as lead, mercury, cadmium, arsenic etc, can be very harmful to humans and the environment [27]. These metals can accumulate in the body over time and lead to diverse health issues, including neurological damage, organ damage, developmental problems in children, and an increased risk of certain cancers. Various sources of exposure include contaminated water, food, air, and consumer products. It is very important to minimize exposure and follow necessary safety guidelines, in order to reduce the risk of adverse health effects.

Heavy metals are elements with high atomic weights and density. These metals are naturally occurring in the environment, but various human activities like industrial processes, mining, and agriculture can release them into the air, water, and soil, leading to increased exposure & contact [28].

Exposure to heavy metals can occur through various pathways:

- i. Ingestion - The consumption of contaminated food and water is a common route of exposure. Plants and animals can take up heavy metals from the soil and water, making them part of the food chain. Seafood, for example, can contain high levels of mercury due to bioaccumulation.
- ii. Inhalation - Breathing in airborne particles or fumes that contain heavy metals, such as lead from leaded gasoline or industrial emissions, can lead to direct absorption through the lungs, eventually causing damage and health issues.
- iii. Dermal Contact - Certain heavy metals can be absorbed through the skin, especially if they come into direct contact with the skin. This is evident for individuals who work with heavy metals in various manufacturing industries.

The health effects of heavy metal exposure can be severe:

i. Neurological Effects - Heavy metals like lead and mercury can cause damage to the nervous system, leading to cognitive deficits, learning disabilities, and behavioral issues, amnesia etc especially in children.

ii. Organ Damage - Kidneys, liver, and other vital organs can be adversely affected by a huge exposure to metals like cadmium, leading to chronic diseases and even organ failure.

iii. Cancer Risk - Some heavy metals, e.g arsenic, are classified as carcinogens and can increase the risk of cancers, including lung, bladder, and skin cancers.

iv. Developmental Issues - Prenatal exposure of pregnant mothers to heavy metals can cause developmental problems in unborn children, affecting growth, cognitive development, and overall health.

v. Cardiovascular Effects - Some heavy metals have been linked to cardiovascular issues, including hypertension and heart disease.

vi. Reproductive Problems - Heavy metal exposure can lead to reproductive disorders to both men and women, affecting fertility and the health of the offspring.

Given the severe nature of health risks, it is very important to take steps in order to

minimize exposure:

- i. Water and Food Safety - Consume clean and well-cooked foods, and drink safe, clean water. Be aware of local advisories about fish consumption, especially for pregnant women and young children.

- ii. Personal Protection - Individuals that works in industries where heavy metal exposure is a concern, should follow all safety protocols, wear protective gear, good usage of industrial equipment and practice good/proper hygiene.

- iii. Environmental Regulations - The government and corporate organizations should ensure strict regulations on industrial emissions and waste disposal to prevent heavy metal contamination of air, water, and soil.

- iv. Regular Testing - Always test your environment, especially if you suspect heavy metal contamination. This can include testing your home's water source and soil to know the level of contamination it possesses.

- v. Proper Disposal - Disposal of electronic waste, organic wastes containing heavy metals should be disposed properly to ensure safety to human health.

By being informed and taking necessary precautions, you can help protect yourself and your community from the risks associated with heavy metal exposure.

2.11 The bioaccumulation of heavy metals in plants and humans

Bioaccumulation refers to the gradual accumulation of substances, such as heavy metals, in living organisms over time. In plants, heavy metals from contaminated soil or water can be taken up through their roots and accumulate in various plant tissues [29]. When humans consume these plants or animals that have ingested these plants, the accumulated heavy metals can potentially enter the human body and cause damage to the vital organs present in humans.

Heavy metals like lead, mercury, cadmium, and arsenic are toxic and can have harmful effects on human health. They can accumulate in tissues such as the liver, kidneys, and bones, leading to various health issues including neurological problems, kidney damage, and even cancer. Edible plants are major sources of diet to human food and their contamination to toxic metals may result to catastrophic health hazards [30].

It is important to monitor and regulate the presence of heavy metals in the environment, especially in areas where human exposure is likely, to prevent excessive bioaccumulation and its associated health risks.

2.11.1 Bio-chemical synthesis of heavy metals in soils around dumpsites

Biochemical synthesis of heavy metals in soils of dumpsites usually refers to the process where microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, that plays a role in accumulating and transforming the various heavy metals present in the soil. These microorganisms can interact with heavy metals through various mechanisms like adsorption, precipitation, and reduction. It can lead to the formation of compounds or minerals that may be less toxic or more stable.

However, it's important to note that the biochemical processes involving heavy metals in dumpsite soils are quite complex and can vary based on factors like the types of heavy metals, the composition of the soil, the types of microorganisms present, and environmental conditions. While some microorganisms have the ability to mitigate the toxicity of heavy metals, the accumulation of heavy metals in soils can still pose significant environmental and health risks. To minimize potential health problems arising from dumpsites, it is substantive that special attention should be paid to sustainable and eco-friendly remedial measures [31].

Proper waste management practices and remediation techniques are crucial to address these problems.

2.11.2. Phytochemicals and chemo chemicals role in effective waste management

Phytochemicals and chemo chemicals plays an important role in effective waste management, particularly in the context of remediation and treatment of contaminated sites [32].

Phytochemicals are naturally occurring compounds found in plants. Many of these compounds have properties that can assist in waste management and environmental remediation. Here's how they can be utilized:

i. **Phytoremediation** - Some plants have the ability to absorb and accumulate contaminants, including heavy metals and organic pollutants, from the soil.

Phytochemicals like organic acids and enzymes are released by plant roots that can enhance this process. These plants, known as hyperaccumulators, can be strategically planted in contaminated areas to help detoxify the soil over time. Also, the indirect

stimulation of heavy metal phyto chemical extraction via the activities of microorganisms associated with the production of biologically active components such as phytohormones (Auxins, gibberellins & Cytokinins) affect the growth and development of plants and organic acids and other classes of compounds [33].

ii. Phytoextraction - Certain phytochemicals facilitate the uptake of pollutants into plant tissues. After the plants are grown and harvested, they can be removed from the site, effectively removing all contaminants from the environment.

iii. Phyto-degradation - Phytochemicals produced by plants can break down or transform pollutants into less toxic forms. This can include organic pollutants, pesticides, and even some heavy metals.

Chemochemicals:

Chemochemicals, on the other hand, are chemical substances that are often used for their reactive properties in waste treatment. They can include various types of compounds and agents that aid in waste management processes:

i. Chemical Precipitation - Chemochemicals can be used to induce precipitation reactions that cause contaminants to solidify or become insoluble. This is often used to remove heavy metals from wastewater.

ii. Chemical Redox Reactions - Chemochemicals can be employed to chemically oxidize or reduce contaminants, transforming them into less harmful forms. This is very useful

for treating organic pollutants in dumpsites.

iii. Chemical Stabilization - Chemochemicals can be used to stabilize contaminants, making them less likely to leach into the environment. This is commonly used for hazardous waste containment.

Role in Effective Waste Management

Both phytochemicals and Chemochemicals contribute to effective waste management in several ways:

i. Sustainable Remediation - Phytochemicals harness the natural capabilities of plants to remove, detoxify, or transform contaminants, providing a more sustainable approach to facilitate waste management.

ii. Cost Efficiency - Phytochemical-based methods can often be cost-effective compared to traditional mechanical or chemical methods of waste management.

iii. Environmental Benefits - Both phytochemical and Chemochemical methods can often minimize disturbance to the environment compared to other waste management remediation process.

iv. Tailored Solutions - Chemochemical treatments can be specifically tailored to a specific type of contaminants and the characterization of the solution and the dumpsites can also be determined for a precise/well defined remediation.

5. Long-Term Solutions - Phytochemical-based approaches, while generally slower, offer long-term solutions for waste management, as they can improve soil quality and reduce the risks of a potential re-release of contaminants that may arise.

It's important to note that the effectiveness of both phytochemical and chemochemical approaches depends on factors such as the type and concentration of contaminants, the properties of the soil and waste droppings in the dumpsites, and environmental conditions. Consulting with environmental experts and using a combination of a defined approach often yields the best results in waste management.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Apparatus and Equipment's

The various apparatus and equipment's used to carry out the collection of sample in this research work includes the following:

- i. Polythene bags
- ii Digger
- iii Trowel
- iv 100 ml volumetric flask
- v 100 ml measuring cylinder
- vi 250 ml beakers

vii pH meter

viii Chemical weighing balance

ix Mesh sieve

x. Meter rule

3.2. Reagents

Distilled H₂O

Standard buffer solutions (pH 4.0-7.0)

Concentrated HCl

Concentrated HNO₃

3.3. Sample collection

The collection of the soil samples was carried out at different dumpsites around Nekede Axis, of Owerri West Local government area, in Imo state, Nigeria.

3.4 Sample technique

The technique employed in this research work, was soil samples collection at three different dumpsites. They were obtained at a depth of 10-15 cm by the use of a digger for digging, trowel for fetching, pH meter for measuring the level of acidity and alkalinity present in the soil, beaker for collecting the solid samples filterates, volumetric flask for giving a precise volumetric analysis content of the sample, weighing balance for determining the weight of the soil sample, meter rule for measurement, polythene bags

for packaging the samples and also taken to get laboratory for preparation and analysis.

3.5 Sample preparation

The wet soils were dried by placing them on a paper like surface, to dry for 3 days. They were also kept in a good place for sunlight to penetrate it. After it was dried, a mesh sieve was used to discard the coarse particles present in the soil, and stored for analysis.

3.6 The pH determination

The pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution of 4.0 & 7.0. it was determined with a soil ratio of 1:2 of distilled water.

3.7 Method

10g of the sieved dry soil, was put into a beaker and then with distilled water 25 ml and stirred for about 30 minutes. The soil suspension was allowed to settle for another 30 minutes, an electrode was immersed in the beaker but not touching the bottom of the beaker.

The pH reading was taken, after 30secs. to give a detailed reading.

3.8 The use of atomic absorption spectroscopy

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) is a widely used analytical technique for quantifying the concentration of heavy metals in various samples, including dumpsites. It offers high sensitivity, accuracy, and selectivity, making it an excellent method for environmental monitoring and assessment [34].

AAS is based on the principle that atoms absorb light of specific wavelengths when they

transition from their ground state to an excited state. The concentration of a particular element in a sample is determined by measuring the absorption of light at a specific wavelength corresponding to that element [35].

Sample Collection and Preparation

Samples from dumpsites need to be collected and prepared before analysis. This involves taking representative samples of soil, water, or other relevant materials from different areas of the dumpsite. The samples are then processed to remove any interfering substances and to bring them into a suitable form for analysis. This might involve digestion, filtration, or extraction processes [36].

Instrumentation:

A typical AAS setup consists of three main components: a radiation source (hollow cathode lamp), a sample introduction system (nebulizer and burner), and a detector (photomultiplier tube). [37].

The hollow cathode lamp emits light at the characteristic wavelength of the metal being analyzed. The sample introduction system converts the sample into a fine aerosol that is then transported into the flame. The detector measures the intensity of light absorbed by the sample [38].

Measurement Procedure:

- i. The hollow cathode lamp emits light of a specific wavelength that corresponds to the absorption line of the target heavy metal element.
- ii. The sample solution is aspirated into the nebulizer, where it forms a fine aerosol.

- iii. The aerosol is introduced into the flame, which atomizes the sample, converting the elements into their free atoms.
- iv. As the atoms absorb light at their characteristic wavelength, the photomultiplier tube detects the decrease in intensity of the emitted light.
- v. The degree of light absorption is directly proportional to the concentration of the element in the sample.

Calibration and Quantification:

To determine the concentration of heavy metals in the samples, a calibration curve is constructed using standard solutions with known concentrations [39]. These standards are treated in the same way as the samples during the analysis. By measuring the absorption intensity of each standard, a calibration curve relating concentration to absorbance is generated. The concentration of heavy metals in the dumpsite samples can then be determined by comparing their absorbance values to the calibration curve [40].

Advantages of AAS in Dumpsite Analysis:

- i Sensitivity - AAS can detect heavy metals at low concentrations, crucial for environmental assessment.
- ii Selectivity - AAS is highly specific to individual elements, reducing the likelihood of interference from other compounds.

iii Accuracy - With proper calibration and sample preparation, AAS provides accurate results.

iv Wide Element Range - AAS can analyze a variety of heavy metals, making it suitable for comprehensive dumpsite analysis.

v Reliability - AAS has been widely accepted and standardized for heavy metal analysis.

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy is an essential technique for determining heavy metal concentrations in dumpsite samples due to its sensitivity, accuracy, and selectivity. It facilitates understanding the extent of heavy metal pollution, facilitating appropriate environmental management strategies [41].

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A tabular representation of all 3 dumpsites showing Results of Heavy metal

Concentration (mg/kg) Nekede, Owerri L.G.A, Imo State

DUMPSITE A

S/N	SAMPLE Sites	PH Levels	Pb	Ni	Cr	Al	Cd	As
1.	A1	6.250	1.550 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.550 ₃ + <u>0.003</u>	0.245 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.082 ₄ + <u>0.00</u>	0.75 ₃ + <u>0.004</u>	0.650 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>
2.	A2	6.050	0.350 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>	0.450 ₂ + <u>0.002</u>	0.039 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.073 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>	0.070 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.055 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>
3.	A3	7.000	0.530 _{0.004} + <u>0.004</u>	0.602 _{0.004} + <u>0.004</u>	0.005 _{0.010} + <u>0.00</u>	0.355 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.650 ₁ + <u>0.00</u>	0.040 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>
	Mean	6.430	0.810 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>	0.534 _{0.003} + <u>0.003</u>	0.289 _{0.007} + <u>0.007</u>	0.170 _{0.003} + <u>0.003</u>	0.265 _{0.002} + <u>0.002</u>	0.053 _{0.002} + <u>0.002</u>

DUMPSITE B

S/N	SAMPLE Sites	PH Levels	Pb	Ni	Cr	Al	Cd	As
1.	B1	6.450	1.250 ₁ + <u>0.00</u>	0.007 ₂ + <u>0.002</u>	0.245 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.082 ₄ + <u>0.00</u>	0.75 ₃ + <u>0.004</u>	0.650 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>
2.	B2	6.050	0.450 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>	0.450 ₂ + <u>0.001</u>	0.003 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.073 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>	0.070 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.055 ₃ + <u>0.00</u>
3.	B3	7.000	1.020 _{0.004} + <u>0.004</u>	0.602 _{0.004} + <u>0.004</u>	0.102 _{0.003} + <u>0.003</u>	0.355 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.650 ₁ + <u>0.00</u>	0.040 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>
	Mean	6.500	0.906 ₂ + <u>0.00</u>	0.037 _{0.006} + <u>0.006</u>	0.062 _{0.003} + <u>0.003</u>	0.142 _{0.003} + <u>0.003</u>	0.053 _{0.002} + <u>0.002</u>	0.202 _{0.002} + <u>0.002</u>

DUMPSITE C

S/ N	SAMPL E Sites	PH Levels	Pb	Ni	Cr	Al	Cd	As
1.	C1	6.750	1.380 _{±0.006}	0.065 _{±0.003}	0.24 _{±0.004}	0.650 _{±0.003}	0.070 _{±0.002}	0.480 _{±0.002}
2.	C2	6.500	0.009 _{±0.003}	0.375 _{±0.004}	0.470 _{±0.003}	0.540 _{±0.002}	0.035 _{±0.003}	0.053 _{±0.001}
3.	C3	6.720	1.350 _{±0.002}	0.025 _{±0.003}	0.050 _{±0.002}	0.250 _{±0.001}	0.025 _{±0.002}	0.045 _{±0.002}
	Mean	6.690	0.933 _{±0.003}	0.155 _{±0.003}	0.183 _{±0.003}	0.480 _{±0.002}	0.243 _{±0.002}	0.192 _{±0.001}

The dumpsites showing their various pH levels & concentration of the Heavy metals in the soil.

KEY:

Dumpsite A – Heavy metals presence and concentration levels of A
 Dumpsite B - Heavy metals presence and concentration levels of B
 Dumpsite C - Heavy metals presence and concentration levels of C.

**DUMPSITE A
(METAL CONCENTRATIONS)**

	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Mean Value
Pb	0.35	1.55	0.003	0.810
Ni	0.45	0.55	0.003	0.534
Cr	0.005	0.245	0.007	0.289
Ai	0.075	0.355	0.003	0.170
Cd	0.04	0.065	0.002	0.053
As	0.037	0.53	0.002	0.202

**DUMPSITE B
(METAL CONCENTRATIONS)**

	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Mean Value
Pb	0.45	1.25	0.002	0.906
Ni	0.003	0.102	0.006	0.037
Cr	0.035	0.105	0.003	0.062
Ai	0.355	0.504	0.003	0.142
Cd	0.25	0.65	0.002	0.450
As	0.037	0.53	0.002	0.202

**DUMPSITE C
(METAL CONCENTRATIONS)**

	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Mean Value
Pb	0.069	1.38	0.003	0.933
Ni	0.025	0.375	0.003	0.155
Cr	0.024	0.47	0.003	0.002
Ai	0.25	0.65	0.002	0.480
Cd	0.025	0.07	0.002	0.243

Descriptive statistics of physicochemical properties of heavy metal concentrations in the soil.

4.1 Results

Fig 4.1 Heavy metal concentration in dumpsite A

Fig 4.2 Heavy metal concentration in dumpsite B

Fig 4.3 Heavy metal concentration in dumpsite C

KEY

MEAN – Average three Soil Samples.

SD ($\pm$) Standard Deviation

Heavy Metals Maximum Level (parts Per Million)

Arsenic (AS) 20

Cadmium (CD) 3

Cobalt (Co) 30

Chromium (Cr) 100

Copper (Cu) 100

Iron (Fe) 5000

Manganese (Mn) 2000

Lead (Pb) 50

Nickel (Ni) 100

Selenium (Se) 10

Zinc (Zn) 300

Source: WHO & FAO

4.2 Discussion

The pH of the soils of the various dumpsites around Nekede, for dumpsite A it was recorded as 6.430, dumpsite B 6.500, and dumpsite C 6.690.

From the results obtained, it clearly indicates that all soil samples from these dumpsites are in an alkaline medium i.e pH above 6.0. The samples of dumpsite A shows the concentration(mg/kg) of heavy metals as follows: Pb(0.810mg/kg), Ni(0.534mg/kg), Cr(0.289mg/kg), Al(0.170mg/kg), Cd(0.265mg/kg), As(0.053mg/kg)

For dumpsite B, the concentrations were, Pb(0.906mg/kg), Ni(0.037mg/kg), Cr(0.062mg/kg), Al(0.142mg/kg), Cd(0.450mg/kg) As(0.202mg/kg).

For dumpsite C, the concentrations were, Pb(0.933mg/kg), Ni(0.155mg/kg), Cr(0.183mg/kg), Al(0.480mg/kg), Cd(0.243mg/kg), As(0.192mg/kg). Pb was detected in all the dumpsites and appears to be higher as found in the respective tables above, this can be attributed to the presence of lead containing wastes at the dumpsites which were eventually leached into the soil. Lead is said to possess some harmful effect at lower levels and no known/established safe levels. Its high degree of exposure is very harmful to human health and may cause harmful effects, e.g neurological disorders, kidney damage, reproductive issues, cardiovascular effects, anemia etc.

Nickel was found in little quantities, but clearly existed in the dumpsites, the low concentrations could be attributed to the lack of industries/ industrial activity around Nekede.

Chromium was also detected in all the dumpsites, although it was quite low, and can also be attributed to the lack of human activities that are capable of generating chromium. Cr +3 is of a lesser damage to health due it its absorption by the human body, but Cr +6 is very poisonous on contact with the human skin.it triggers allergies and irritations, and is therefore considered to be carcinogenic to humans.

Aluminum and cadmium had low concentrations also, the can also be attributed to various sources which include, automobile tire dust, burning of oil and tyre, plastic wrappings, paints and dyes etc. The various levels of all the heavy metals present in these dumpsites fall within the acceptable limit set by world health organization. Therefore the results show a low amount of wastes, carrying less concentration of these metals (Pb,Ni, Cr,Al,Cd,As) in Nekede.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

The research study investigates a determination of heavy metal presence in dumpsites in Nekede, Owerri West L.G.A, Imo state, Nigeria.

The results clearly indicates that most of the areas were shown to have concentrations of heavy metals, although not all heavy metals could be detected on the dumpsites, it was also observed, that some dumpsites have a higher concentration of these metals,

due to the presence of waste having great quantities of heavy metals. Other sites of lower heavy metal concentration, may be as a result of lower concentration. this may be as a result of low contamination, due to human activities or none existent at all.

Although the results obtained may not pose any serious implications at the moment, there may be a cause for concern in the future, due to the accumulation of heavy metals, and may pose a great health risk.

5.2 Conclusion

From the research study, all the dumpsites contains most of these heavy metals. It was also observed that some dumpsites had a higher concentration than others. The heavy metals concentration in these dumpsites are all within WHO limits, except Pb, Cd & Cr which are slightly above this limits. It is also of great importance to focus on the potential risks these dumpsites may have in the future if any.

5.3 Recommendations

Reducing the impact of heavy metals on the environment is crucial for sustainability and effective waste management control, it can be implemented in the following ways:

Reduce Emissions - Implement strict regulations on industries to reduce emissions of heavy metals into the air and water. This includes controlling releases from mining, manufacturing, and power generation from power plants.

Waste Management -Properly manage and dispose of electronic waste and batteries, which contain heavy metals like lead, mercury, and cadmium. Encourage recycling and

safe disposal methods.

Soil Remediation - Remediate contaminated soils through techniques like phytoremediation (using plants to absorb and accumulate heavy metals) or chemical treatments.

Water Treatment - Improve wastewater treatment processes to remove heavy metals from industrial effluents before they enter natural water bodies.

Monitor Water Sources - Regularly monitor water quality in rivers, lakes, and groundwater to detect and address contamination promptly.

Education and Awareness - Educate communities and industries about the hazards of heavy metals and promote responsible usage and disposal.

Addressing heavy metal pollution is a multifaceted challenge that requires a combination of regulatory, technological, educational, and societal efforts.

Collaboration between governments, industries, NGO's (Non-governmental organizations) and local communities is essential for effective solutions.

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